

Article

The Effect of Biobased N and P Fertilizers in a Winter Wheat–Ryegrass Crop Rotation

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Abstract: Novel recycled fertilizers could help close environmental nutrient cycles in the circular economy. To better understand their performance and residual value, commercially available biobased nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) fertilizers (BBFs) were tested in a two-year crop cycle of winter wheat and ryegrass. The N fertilizer replacement value of N-BBFs ranged from 47 to 80% in the main crop. Not all BBFs led to a similarly high N concentration in the mineral reference wheat straw. However, full and early fertilization with incorporation could make the fertilizing effect of N-BBFs more reliable. The P fertilizer replacement value ranged between 105 and 161% for the crop cycle. We assume that the N contained in biobased phosphorus fertilizers can be seen as unproblematic for losses during winter and can serve as a starter fertilizer already present in the soil for the succeeding crop in spring. In general, biobased P fertilizers had a higher residual value than biobased N fertilizers. However, these residual values were comparable to those of mineral fertilizer references. While P-BBFs proved to be a sustainable and reliable nutrient source for a crop cycle, the N-BBFs used as the main crop fertilizer were found to be more prone to environmental influences.

Keywords: biobased fertilizers; BBF; crop rotation; nitrogen; phosphorus; *Lolium perenne*; ryegrass; *Triticum aestivum*; winter wheat; residual effect; mineral fertilizer replacement; nutrient offtake

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1. Introduction

With a growing world population and decreasing land resources [1], further intensification of current agricultural production is inevitable. The use of mineral fertilizers has contributed to achieving high yields by supplying crops with nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P), which are limiting growth factors. However, the excessive use of mineral fertilizers is highly criticized and associated with irreversible consequences for the environment [2]. Industrial atmospheric N fixation is energy intensive [3–6], and P fertilizer production depends on non-renewable mineral deposits [7–9]. Due to currently open nutrient cycles, both nutrients are introduced into natural ecosystems with devastating consequences [10,11]. The resulting negative environmental effects and political dependencies caused by the lack of P resources within the European Union lead to an urgent need to find alternative fertilizers. Recycled nutrients from urban organic waste streams, the food processing industry, or agricultural production may provide an alternative fertilizer source.

In 2020, the European Commission adopted the new circular economy action plan (CEAP) to transform the EU into a circular economy (CE) [12]. Reusing resources from waste streams is part of the CE concept. It implements the reuse of materials and the closing of product and nutrient loops to avoid material and nutrient losses. In this way, energy demand, environmental damage, and resource requirements for fertilizer production can be decreased [13]. The use of biobased fertilizers (BBFs) produced from nutrient-rich side

streams (NRSS) is one way to recycle nutrients such as N and P [14]. Here, BBFs can be an opportunity to contribute to closing the nutrient cycle in agricultural production, in line with the CE concept.

The diverse NRSS used as source materials and processing options result in a wide variety of BBFs with different potentials to replace conventional fertilizers. BBFs are mostly obtained from bio-waste streams, such as food waste, sewage sludge, and agricultural waste, which may contain plant and forest residues, cereal biomass, and animal manure [14]. The main production procedures for BBFs are composting, anaerobic digestion, incineration, and pyrolysis [14]. However, the use of NRSS for fertilizer production carries the risk of spreading contaminants and other hazardous substances [15,16].

The potential of BBFs to create a sustainable CE is high. The properties of BBFs depend on multiple factors (e.g., production process, process conditions, source material). It is, therefore, important to assess their fertilizing efficiency and potential to replace synthetic or mined fertilizers. Due to their novelty, potential pollutants, such as heavy metals, should also be assessed [17]. Scientifically sound knowledge regarding the medium- or long-term influence of BBFs on crop growth and physiology is valuable and urgently needed, but so far only a few studies have focused on medium- or long-term time spans or crop rotation.

To test BBFs for their potential effectiveness in agriculture, on-farm or at least field experiments are recommended, but their realization requires large efforts in terms of labor and financial resources. They also involve more risks due to various adverse external factors. In contrast, greenhouse studies allow many different treatments to be tested, but their duration is usually limited as the pot size restricts the root growth of the test crops. Transferring findings from the greenhouse to field conditions should be performed with caution, if at all. To overcome these obstacles associated with pot trials and to ensure the transferability to field conditions, a large-scale container study was established, combining the advantages of both approaches. Based on the findings of [18–22], we chose containers with a volume of 240 L, mainly to allow extensive root development in a longer study duration, so that pot size does not become a limiting factor in this study, but also to approximate the hydrodynamics of natural soils as a factor of soil chemical dynamics [23–25]. The containers were set up outside, surrounded by a wire cage, to simulate field conditions, but with the exclusion of certain external influences that could interfere with the experiment, e.g., animals and extreme drought.

The overall objective of this study was to test six selected P- and six N-BBFs obtained from different raw materials over a two-year crop rotation in field-like growing conditions. The specific objectives were to set up and test a container trial over a longer period than one growing season, to evaluate the potential effects of BBFs on the growth of winter wheat and ryegrass and to assess the effect of BBFs on soil properties.

The following hypotheses were tested:

- N-BBFs can supply the fertilized crop with N as efficiently as mineral N fertilizers.
- P-BBFs can supply plants with P in a crop rotation as efficiently as water-soluble mineral fertilizers.
- Heavy metals in BBFs accumulate in crop biomass to a different extent than with conventional fertilizers and this depends on the source material of the BBF.
- BBFs differ in the provision of organic carbon to the soil and in plant P availability after a two-year crop rotation.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Container Setup and Site

The soil used in this trial (clay 31%, sand 2%, silt 67%; pH 6.92) was obtained from an experimental field station of the University of Hohenheim near Renningen (48.744367° N, 8.924009° E). To prevent the soil from swelling and shrinking during the experiment, it was mixed with sand (0.063–2 mm) from the Rhine Valley in a concrete mixer. The mixing ratio was 55% sand and 45% original soil on a weight basis. The substrate was filled into large-volume containers (240 L; surface area of 0.29 m²) after a drainage level was placed

in the bottom of the containers with gravel (16–32 mm), fleece, and a valve (Figure 1). The filling resulted in an average thickness of the drainage level of 13 cm, subsoil of 77 cm, and topsoil of 10 cm. After filling the containers, a mixed sample was taken from all containers to determine the pH value (6.51), plant-available N (N_{\min} ; 14 kg ha^{-1}), and plant-availability of P ($2.52 \text{ mg P(CAL)} (100 \text{ g substrate})^{-1}$) at the start of the trial. This CAL-P is considered low [26]. One year after filling the soil substrate into the containers, the grain size fractionation of the test soil was again determined. This resulted in a fractionation of 13% clay, 54% sand, and 33% silt.

Figure 1. Design of containers with the winter wheat–ryegrass crop rotation over time. The container on the left shows a cross-section with the drainage level (13 cm) and the subsoil level (77 cm) plus topsoil (10 cm). Drawn with Adobe Illustrator (Version 20.0).

Throughout the entire experiment, the containers were set up in a wire cage to mimic outdoor field conditions, such as storms, frost, and natural solar radiation, while being protected from certain external influences, e.g., birds and other animals. Waterlogging within the containers was prevented by drainage levels with drain taps (Figure 1). Weather data were obtained from a nearby weather station (48.6883° N , 9.2235° E) [27] (Figure 2). The containers were only watered on the days following the sowing of crops to ensure uniform emergence of the seedlings. Thereafter, the containers were only irrigated when drought stress symptoms were visible on the plants (e.g., during a dry period in April/May 2020) to ensure the continuation of the experiment.

Figure 2. Average monthly temperature (dotted line) and precipitation (bars) during the growing period of winter wheat and ryegrass from April 2020 to November 2022. Data from DWD [27].

2.2. Management and Crop Rotation

On 2 November 2020, winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L. cv. Apostel) was sown by hand using a self-made sowing stamp at a rate of 105 grains per container and a depth of 2.5 cm (Figures 3 and 4A,B). The seeds were dressed in fungicides (“Landor CT” = fludioxonil, difenoconazol, tebuconazol). Five days after sowing, manual harrowing (depth 1 cm) was performed to soften the soil surface and destroy emerging weeds. In the spring and summer of 2021, the winter wheat was harrowed again (depth 1 cm) to incorporate the first and second N fertilization. In between, weeding was performed by hand when necessary. The weeds were not removed from the containers but left on the surface. After harvesting, the top 3 cm of the soil was tilled with a hand hoe several times over two weeks to manage the volunteer grain. Then, ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.) was sown at a rate of 1.3 g per container. During the ryegrass cultivation phase, weeds were pulled out by hand and left on the surface of the container they came from (Figure 4 C,D).

Figure 3. Sowing stamp. Containers stamped with holes at the front, sown containers at the back.

Figure 4. Impressions of the container trial. (A): Winter wheat in April 2021; (B): Winter wheat in July 2021; (C): Ryegrass in October 2021 before the first cut; (D): Ryegrass in October 2021 after the first cut.

2.3. Fertilizers and Fertilization

A basal fertilization of 113 kg Mg ha⁻¹, 800 kg K ha⁻¹, 152 kg S ha⁻¹ was applied to the containers (0.00029 ha) and incorporated to a depth of 10 cm two weeks before sowing winter wheat to ensure that these plant nutrients would not become a limiting factor in the trial. In total, sixteen fertilizer types were applied to four complete blocks, each with a grid of 4 × 4 containers.

The P-BBFs (Table 1) were applied and incorporated on 2 November 2020, a few hours before sowing the winter wheat (Table 2). The N-BBFs (Table 1) were applied to the growing winter wheat in two doses in spring (1.5 cm) and summer (top dressing) 2021 (Table 2). As reference treatments, the corresponding mineral fertilizers (N, P, N + P) (Table 1) were applied at the same time as the N- and P-BBFs. Calcium ammonium nitrate (CAN) and triple superphosphate (TSP) were used as mineral N and P references, respectively.

Table 1. Categorized fertilizers, acronyms used in the trial with description, and the N, P, K contents in % of FW.

	Fertilizer Name	Acronym	Description *	N (% of FW)	P (% of FW)	K (% of FW)
References	Control	Control	No fertilization	-	-	-
	Reference 1	TSP + CAN	Mineral N and P	27 *	20.5	0.24
	Reference 2	CAN	Mineral N	27 *	0 *	0 *
	Reference 3	TSP	Mineral P	0 *	20.5	0.24
P-BBFs	Monterra	MO14	Animal proteins, vegetable byproducts, pelletizing	2.36	6.63	3.32 *
	Meat and bone meal	MB1	MBM, pelletizing	8.12	6.15	0.44
	Chicken manure	OPU	chicken manure, pelletizing	3.19	1.61	2.04
	Struvite	CGO	Struvite precipitated from wastewater	10.1	12.4	0
	AshDec	ADC	SSA, thermochemical process	0.05	8.04	1.21
	Manure biochar	MBC	Chicken manure, energy-free carbonization technology	2.93	3.04	4.94
N-BBFs	Palaterra CV	PAL	Fermented biochar and high-quality clay and rock flour	4.89	0.87	4.98
	Bioagenasol	BA6	Plant-based residue (wheat and maize), fermentation and distillation	5.57	1.23	1.30
	SIFORGA-BIO	SIF	Animal and vegetal raw materials, granulating	9.92	0.43 *	2.49 *
	MALTaflor bio	MAL	Mixture of malt germ, malt, minerals, and vinasse vegetable, drying and pelletizing	4.37	0.40	4.10
	Øgro N15	OG2	Horn meal (pig bristles), hydrolysis	13.9	0.30	0.01
	Monterra	MO13	Feather meal, pelletizing	14.2	0	0

FW, fresh weight; TSP, triple superphosphate; CAN, calcium ammonium nitrate. * = data obtained from the BBF producers.

Table 2. Application plan for mineral fertilizer and BBFs for the crop rotation in 2020 and 2021 with P and N application rates in reference and BBF treatments.

Year	2020	2021	2021
Season	Fall (2 November 2020)	Spring (8 April 2021)	Summer (3 June 2021)
Control			
Reference 1 N + P	84 kg P ha ⁻¹	115 kg N ha ⁻¹	115 kg N ha ⁻¹
Reference 2 N	-	115 kg N ha ⁻¹	115 kg N ha ⁻¹
Reference 3 P	84 kg P ha ⁻¹	-	-
P-BBFs	84 kg P ha ⁻¹ (as BBFs)	115 kg N ha ⁻¹	115 kg N ha ⁻¹
N-BBFs	84 kg P ha ⁻¹	115 kg N ha ⁻¹ (as BBFs)	115 kg N ha ⁻¹ (as BBFs)

The N fertilization was calculated based on the N removal of winter wheat [28], assuming a N removal of 230 kg N ha⁻¹ for a grain yield of 8 t ha⁻¹. The P fertilization was based on the sum of the P removal of winter wheat at 36 kg P ha⁻¹, one ryegrass cut in 2021 (4 t TM ha⁻¹ $\hat{=}$ 2 kg P ha⁻¹), and up to six ryegrass cuts in 2022 (12 t TM ha⁻¹ $\hat{=}$ 46 kg P ha⁻¹) [29] (Table 2). N-BBFs treatments were fertilized with the full amount of P in form of TSP, and P-BBFs treatments were fertilized in the same way with N using CAN (Table 2).

Some of the N- and P-BBFs not only supplied the relevant nutrient (i.e., N or P) but also certain amounts of the other nutrient (P or N) in varying quantities (Table 3). The amount of CAN and TSP was not reduced based on the additional nutrients provided by the BBFs since they are not necessarily plant available and also to approximate practical agriculture.

Table 3. Amount of N/P applied to each container through the application of N-/P-BBFs, in g per container and kg ha⁻¹.

P-BBF	g N Container ⁻¹	kg N ha ⁻¹	N-BBF	g P Container ⁻¹	kg P ha ⁻¹
MB1	3.146	108	PAL	0.893	31
CGO	1.093	38	BA6	1.306	45
ADC	0.015	1	SIF	0.293	10
OPU	4.011	138	MAL	0.666	23
MO14	0.798	28	OG2	0.084	3
MBC	2.281	79	MO13	0	0

After harvesting winter wheat at UHOH in 2021, all 64 containers received a small amount of mineral N fertilizer ($\hat{=}$ 35 kg N ha⁻¹) to ensure an even emergence of the following crop, ryegrass.

2.4. Measurements, Harvests, and Sampling

2.4.1. SPAD Measurements

A SPAD meter (SPAD-502Plus, KONICA MINOLTA, Osaka, Japan) was used to measure SPAD (Soil-Plant Analysis Development) values in winter wheat leaves on a weekly basis from BBCH 21 (tillering) to BBCH 59 (flowering). This measurement method uses the direct proportionality of the SPAD values to chlorophyll content and, thus, leaf N concentration [30]. Therefore, the SPAD value allows conclusions to be drawn about the N supply status of plants [31]. SPAD measurements were taken at the midpoint of the uppermost fully developed leaf. In total, 16 representative tillers of the plants were randomly selected for the measurements in each container, and the mean value was calculated.

2.4.2. Harvest and Sampling

During the winter wheat harvest (22 July 2021), all plants were cut 2 cm above the ground and weighed. The ears were separated from the stalks, and then the stalks and ears were weighed again. Due to unseasonably wet weather conditions, the harvest was performed three weeks later than planned, which resulted in considerable grain losses during processing in the high-yielding treatments and heavy grain ears (discussed in Section 2.5.2). After drying (60 °C for 72 h), the dry matter (DM) was determined and the ears were threshed. Grain yield and the thousand grain mass were then determined. Grain and straw samples were ground and analyzed for mineral content and heavy metals. Soil samples (30 cm) were taken from each container and stored at -18 °C for later analysis of plant-available N (N_{min}), P, pH, and organic carbon (C_{org}).

Ryegrass was cut on 22 October 2021, 5 May 2022, 5 July 2022, and 24 October 2022. The plants were cut 1–2 cm above the soil surface and, after determination of the fresh weight (FW), dried at 60 °C for 48 h to determine dry weight. The dried samples were ground and analyzed for N, P, and heavy metals.

2.4.3. Plant and Soil Sample Analyses

Soil or substrate texture was determined by sieving and sedimentation using the ISO 11277 method. The total N concentration in the biomass was determined by the Dumas method (DIN EN 13654-2). Concentrations of P and heavy metals (Fe, Mn, Zn, Mo, Cd, Ni, Cr) were determined by extraction in HNO₃ with microwave digestion followed by ICP-OES measurement (DIN EN ISO 11885).

Plant-available N (NO₃ and NH₄; referred to as N_{min}) was determined in freshly thawed soil by CaCl₂ extraction followed by FIA (flow injection analysis) measurement (DIN ISO 14255:1998-11). Plant-available P was then characterized in air-dried soil by CAL extraction followed by flow injection photometer measurement (OENORM L 1087:2012-12-01). Total C, total N, and organic carbon were determined in air-dried soil by Dumas combustion (CNS vario Macro Cube, Elementar; Germany, Langenselbold) DIN EN 13654-2:2002-01). Soil pH was measured using a glass electrode in a CaCl₂ suspension (DIN ISO 10390:2022-08).

2.5. Statistics and Calculations

2.5.1. Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis of the experiment was performed using SAS software (version 9.4. SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA). A linear mixed model was fitted with treatments as a fixed effect and blocks and rows as random effect. The model can be described as follows:

$$Y_{ikl} = \mu + \alpha_i + \beta_k + \gamma_l + \varepsilon_{ikl} \quad (1)$$

where Y_{ikl} is the observation of treatment i in block k and row l , μ is the intercept, α_i is the effect of fertilizer treatment i , β_k is the random effect of block k , γ_l is the random effect of row l , and ε_{ikl} is the error of Y_{ikl} . Note that block effects were assumed to be random, as some blocks were incomplete due to missing values, which were not linked to treatment effects. Note also that the design was planned as a randomized complete block design and row effects were subsequently fitted via post-blocking to account for a north–south gradient. For most traits, a common tendency for the effect of N- and P-BBFs was visible. Therefore, the model was extended with a grouping factor for N-BBFs and P-BBFs in a separate analysis.

For the ryegrass cut and nutrient offtake, measurements were taken repeatedly over time. Here, model (1) was expanded by the main effect time, interactions of time and treatment, and time-specific row and block effects. Error effects of the same container were allowed to be correlated. Six different structures were fitted: an unstructured variance-covariance structure, a first-order autoregressive with homogeneous or heterogeneous variances, a compound symmetry structure with homogeneous and heterogeneous variances, and an identity matrix with constant variance. The best-fitting variance–covariance matrix was chosen based on the Akaike Information Criterion [32].

$$Y_{ijk} = \mu + \alpha_i + \tau_{j+} + (\alpha\tau)_{ij} + \beta_k + \beta_{jk} + \gamma_l + \gamma_{jl} + \varepsilon_{ijk} \quad (2)$$

where Y_{ijk} is the observation of treatment i in block k and row l at time j , τ_j is the fixed effect of time j , $(\alpha\tau)_{ij}$ is the fixed interaction effect of treatment i and time j , β_{jk} and γ_{jl} are the time-specific block and row effects, and all other effects are defined analogous to model (1).

Due to a pest infestation in some of the containers, the ryegrass could not be harvested in the last cut. Whether the pest had already influenced the yield in previous cuts was tested by adding a categorical factor indicating affected containers in the last cut in the analysis of previous cuts. However, no significant influence was detected, and the observations were included in the estimation of the individual cuts. These containers were excluded from the analysis of the total biomass.

In the first step, pre-requirements of ANOVA, namely homogeneity of variance and normal distribution of residuals, were checked by visual examination of studentized

residual plots. Values of studentized residuals below -3 and above $+3$ were considered outliers and were removed from the dataset. The second step of data analysis was an ANOVA to evaluate the significance of the treatment effect ($\alpha = 0.05$). Where treatment effects were significant, least square means were estimated and pairwise comparisons (Tukey's HSD) were performed.

2.5.2. Estimation of Winter Wheat Yield

The winter wheat harvest was postponed due to rainy weather. In the high-performing fertilization treatments, heavy grains fell out of the ears during the rain and later when the plants were cut for processing. This considerable kernel loss in high-performing treatments but not in treatments without N fertilization (only TSP, Control) led to an underestimation of the high-performing references (CAN + TSP, CAN) and the BBFs. Nevertheless, the SPAD data and nutrient contents of the straw and grains obtained were sufficient to discuss the first-year BBF fertilizing effect (Section 3.1). As we want to calculate a soil nutrient withdrawal of winter wheat to calculate the N and P offtake of the whole crop cycle, an estimation of the winter wheat yield is necessary to determine the nutrient offtake.

The SPAD data of the penultimate measurement (10 June 2021) during flowering, straw dry matter yield, and grain P and N concentration were considered the best indicators of differences between the treatments (Section 3.1). To test our assumption, we determined the relationship between these observations, grain P concentration, and (later) the estimated grain yield using a calculated pairwise Pearson correlation between the traits (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Heatmap of pairwise correlation between traits. ** = $p < 0.01$, *** = $p < 0.001$.

Figure 5 shows a highly significant correlation between SPAD, grain N and straw dry matter. Since the P fertilization effect of all fertilization treatments was not significant (Sections 3.1 and 4) and the correlation of grain P was not as high as the other traits, we used straw dry matter, grain N, and SPAD to estimate the grain yield of winter wheat.

The estimation was based on the grain yield of the unfertilized control that did not lose kernels from the ears:

$$GY = GY_{control} \times \frac{\left(\frac{SY_{treatment}}{SY_{control}}\right) + \left(\frac{SPAD_{treatment}}{SPAD_{control}}\right) + \left(\frac{N_{treatment}}{N_{control}}\right)}{3} \quad (3)$$

where GY is the estimated grain yield. $GY_{control}$ is the grain yield of the control. $SY_{treatment}$ and $SY_{control}$ are the straw yield of the treatment and the control, respectively. $SPAD_{treatment}$ and $SPAD_{control}$ are the SPAD values of the last measuring time point of the treatment and the control, and $N_{treatment}$ and $N_{control}$ are the grain N concentrations of the treatment and the control.

2.5.3. Calculation of Nutrient Offtake and Fertilizer Replacement Values

Nutrient offtake was calculated by multiplying N and P concentrations by yield and aboveground biomass, respectively. Based on these values, N use efficiencies were estimated using the following equation [33]:

$$NUE = \frac{N_{\text{offtake N-BBF}} - N_{\text{offtake control}}}{N_{\text{fertilized}}} \quad (4)$$

where NUE is the N use efficiency, $N_{\text{offtake N-BBF}}$ is the N offtake by N-BBFs, $N_{\text{offtake control}}$ is the N offtake of the unfertilized control, and $N_{\text{fertilized}}$ is the fertilized amount of N. The P use efficiency was calculated analogously.

For the fertilizer replacement values, the nutrient use efficiencies of N and P-BBFs were evaluated relative to the fully fertilized reference (CAN + TSP) using the following equation [34]:

$$NFRV = \frac{NUE_{NBBF}}{NUE_{CAN+TSP}} \quad (5)$$

$NFRV$ is the N fertilizer replacement value, NUE_{NBBF} is the N use efficiency of the N-BBFs, and $NUE_{CAN+TSP}$ is the N use efficiency of the fully fertilized reference. Again, P fertilizer replacement values of the P-BBFs were calculated analogously. All results of this calculation are based on 'Control' and 'TSP only' and can be found in Appendix A (Tables A3–A5). For comparability with other studies, only the results based on 'Control' are discussed in this study.

3. Results

3.1. Winter Wheat Yield, Nutrient Content, and Nutrient Offtake

3.1.1. SPAD Measurements in Winter Wheat

The SPAD measurements during the growth period of winter wheat in spring 2021 showed different patterns for the six N-BBFs (Figure 6) and for the six P-BBFs (Figure 7). The N-BBFs showed a higher scattering of the data for the period from 6 April 2021 (tillering) to 16 June 2021 (flowering) than the P-BBFs. In the last measurement, the SPAD values of the crops treated with N-BBFs were between those of the mineral N references (CAN, CAN + TSP), which had higher SPAD values, and the references without mineral N (Control 0, TSP) with lower values. The P-BBFs had similarly high SPAD values as the N references in the last measurement and showed an overall lower fluctuation of data between tillering and flowering than the N-BBFs.

Figure 6. N-BBF SPAD values of winter wheat (y -axis) at time of measurements in 2021 (x -axis). Mean values of the unfertilized (control) and fertilized references (CAN + TSP, CAN, TSP) are displayed in black.

Mean values of the six N-BBFs (BA6, MAL, MO13, OG2, PAL, SIF) are displayed in orange. For simplified presentation, mean values have been interpolated and are shown without comparisons of means (given in Table A1).

Figure 7. P-BBF SPAD values of winter wheat (y-axis) at time of measurements in 2021 (x-axis). Mean values of the unfertilized (control) and fertilized references (CAN + TSP, CAN, TSP) are displayed in black. Mean values of the six P-BBFs (ADC, MB1, MO14, OPU, CGO, MBC) are displayed in blue. For simplified presentation, mean values have been interpolated and are shown without comparisons of means (given in Table A2).

3.1.2. Straw Dry Mass, Nutrient Contents, and Estimated Winter Wheat Grain Yield

The fertilization treatments showed highly significantly differences from each other in terms of straw dry mass. The P-BBF group had significantly higher straw biomass than the N-BBF group, the unfertilized control, and the reference fertilized with TSP only. However, the straw yield only showed significant differences between CGO and the unfertilized control when the fertilizers were compared individually (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Mean values of straw yield (dry matter) in g per container for all treatments. Blue bars represent P-BBFs, orange bars N-BBFs, and black bars the mineral references or unfertilized (Control 0). Treatments with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Pooled standard error 6.08.

The fertilization treatments differed highly significantly from each other in terms of grain N concentration in. The grain N concentration of winter wheat showed significant

differences between all BBFs and the unfertilized control and the reference fertilized with TSP only (Figure 9). The P-BBF group had significantly higher grain N concentrations than the N-BBF. The N-BBF group had significantly lower N concentrations than “CAN + TSP”.

Figure 9. Mean grain N concentration (%) of winter wheat for all treatments. Blue bars represent P-BBFs, orange bars N-BBFs and black bars the unfertilized (Control 0) and mineral references. The mean values of fertilizers with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Pooled standard error 0.16.

The fertilization treatments differed highly significantly from each other in terms of grain P concentration. Here, winter wheat showed only significantly higher differences between the BBFs OPU, CGO, and MAL on the one hand and the unfertilized control on the other hand (Figure 10). The crops that received N-BBFs were found to have lower grain P concentrations than those that received P-BBFs; however, this was not significant ($p = 0.0577$). Within the P-BBF group, MO14 concentrated significantly less P than CGO. The estimated grain yield showed the lowest yields in the mineral references fertilized without CAN, followed by the N-BBFs. However, the differences between the N and P BBFs and the mineral CAN references were modest (Figure 11).

Figure 10. Mean values of grain P concentration of winter wheat for all treatments. Blue bars represent P-BBFs, orange bars N-BBFs, black bars the unfertilized (Control 0) and mineral references. The mean values of fertilizers with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Pooled standard error 0.22.

Figure 11. Estimated values of winter wheat grain yields for all treatments. Blue bars represent P-BBFs, orange bars N-BBFs, black bars the unfertilized (Control 0) and mineral references. The whiskers show the standard deviation of means for each treatment.

3.1.3. Nutrient Offtake of Winter Wheat

The fertilization treatments differed highly significantly from each other in winter wheat grain, straw, and total N offtake. The BBFs had a significantly higher N offtake in winter wheat straw and grain compared to the unfertilized control and “only TSP”. Here “only CAN” and “CAN + TSP” were significantly higher than the N-BBFs. The P-BBF group also showed significantly higher N offtake than the N-BBF group (Figure 12). The total N offtake followed the same pattern as straw and grain N offtake. The P-BBFs CGO and OPU showed the highest total N offtake of all treatments. The N-BBFs PAL, SIF, and MAL did not differ significantly from the mineral CAN references in total N offtake.

Figure 12. Mean values of N offtake of winter wheat components for all treatments. Blue bars represent P-BBFs, orange bars N-BBFs, black bars the unfertilized (Control 0) and mineral references. The treatments with at least one identical letter per straw-, grain-, and total N offtake are not significantly different from each other (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Pooled standard error 0.44 (grain), 0.19 (straw).

In winter wheat straw, P levels are negligibly low and, thus, P contents were not considered for P offtake [35,36]. The fertilization treatments differed highly significantly from each other in winter wheat P offtake (grain). The BBFs had a significantly higher P offtake compared to the unfertilized control and “only TSP”. Here, “only CAN” and “CAN + TSP” did not differ significantly from the BBFs. The P-BBF group showed significantly higher P offtake than the N-BBF group (Figure 13). The P-BBF “CGO” had the highest P offtake of all BBFs.

Figure 13. Mean values of P offtake of winter wheat (grains) for all treatments. Blue bars represent P-BBFs, orange bars N-BBFs, black bars the unfertilized (Control 0) and mineral references. The treatments with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Pooled standard error 62.8.

3.1.4. Heavy Metal Concentrations in Winter Wheat Grain

The heavy metal concentrations in winter wheat grain showed significant differences for Fe, Zn, Mo, and Cd. The concentrations of Fe, Zn, and Cd were significantly higher in the crops treated with P-BBFs than those treated with N-BBFs, but did not differ from the “CAN + TSP” reference. For Fe, the BBFs OPU, MO14, CGO, and MB1 had significantly higher grain Fe concentrations than the others (Table 4).

Table 4. Heavy metal concentrations of winter wheat grain for all treatments, in mg g⁻¹ for iron (Fe), manganese (Mn), and zinc (Zn), and in $\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ for molybdenum (Mo), cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni), and chromium (Cr). The mean values of heavy metals for treatments with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). For heavy metal values without letters, no significant differences between treatments were detected by Tukey’s test.

Treatment	Element							
	Fe	Mn	Zn	Mo	Cd	Ni	Cr	
	mg g ⁻¹			$\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$				
References	Control	0.029 ^a	0.024	0.006 ^{ab}	0.960 ^c	0.028 ^{abc}	0.334	0.050
	CAN + TSP	0.044 ^{bcd}	0.026	0.036 ^{abc}	0.653 ^a	0.090 ^{abcde}	0.233	0.116
	Only CAN	0.044 ^{bcd}	0.024	0.027 ^{abc}	0.614 ^a	0.091 ^{bcde}	0.114	0.076
	Only TSP	0.027 ^a	0.024	0.004 ^a	0.924 ^{bc}	0.023 ^{ab}	0.104	0.040

Table 4. Cont.

Treatment	Element							
	Fe	Mn	Zn	Mo	Cd	Ni	Cr	
	mg g ⁻¹			µg g ⁻¹				
P-BBFs	MB1	0.049 ^{cd}	0.024	0.046 ^c	0.608 ^a	0.125 ^e	0.286	0.078
	CGO	0.052 ^d	0.027	0.053 ^c	0.651 ^a	0.127 ^e	0.271	0.133
	ADC	0.044 ^{bcd}	0.025	0.036 ^{abc}	0.677 ^a	0.091 ^{bcde}	0.176	0.164
	OPU	0.052 ^d	0.025	0.050 ^c	0.733 ^{abc}	0.105 ^{de}	0.396	0.156
	MO14	0.050 ^d	0.024	0.038 ^{bc}	0.587 ^a	0.099 ^{cde}	0.257	0.103
	MBC	0.042 ^{bcd}	0.024	0.033 ^{abc}	0.584 ^a	0.091 ^{bcde}	0.100	0.131
N-BBFs	OG2	0.033 ^{ab}	0.023	0.009 ^{ab}	0.696 ^{ab}	0.016 ^a	0.223	0.076
	MO13	0.033 ^{ab}	0.024	0.022 ^{abc}	0.764 ^{abc}	0.050 ^{abcd}	0.108	0.111
	PAL	0.042 ^{bcd}	0.027	0.021 ^{abc}	0.645 ^a	0.068 ^{abcde}	0.186	0.073
	BA6	0.035 ^{ab}	0.025	0.007 ^{ab}	0.686 ^a	0.033 ^{abcd}	0.250	0.083
	SIF	0.037 ^{ab}	0.024	0.026 ^{abc}	0.663 ^a	0.054 ^{abcde}	0.115	0.103
	MAL	0.043 ^{bcd}	0.028	0.034 ^{abc}	0.712 ^{ab}	0.071 ^{abcde}	0.282	0.133

3.2. Residual Fertilizer Value

3.2.1. Dry Matter Yield of Ryegrass After Winter Wheat as a Main Crop

All treatments fertilized with N and P resulted in higher total ryegrass dry matter yield than the unfertilized control (Figure 14). The P-BBF group had a significantly higher dry matter yield in the second cut than the N-BBFs and the unfertilized control. The influence of the fertilizers on dry matter yield decreased with each cut over time, so that no significant differences were detected in the fourth cut. The reference “only TSP” was the only treatment that was not significantly different from the unfertilized control in the sum of the dry matter cuts.

Figure 14. Dry matter yield of ryegrass as the sum of four cuts ((1) 22 October 2021; (2) 5 May 2022; (3) 5 July 2022; (4) 26 October 2022). Each section of the bar represents the back-transformed median of the corresponding cut. Identical lower-case letters indicate no significant difference between the treatments for the corresponding cut (1–4) (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Identical upper-case letters indicate no significant difference between the main effects of the treatments. Pooled standard error of transformed data 0.06 (1), 0.09 (2), 0.05 (3), 0.07 (4).

3.2.2. N and P Offtake of Ryegrass After Winter Wheat as a Main Crop

All treatments fertilized with N and P resulted in significantly higher N offtake than the unfertilized reference and the reference fertilized with TSP only (Figure 15). The P-BBF group had a significantly higher total N offtake than the N-BBF group, mainly related to higher N offtakes in the first and second cut. No differences were detected in cuts three and four. The N offtake in the first two cuts was higher for all BBFs than for the references “Control 0” and “only TSP”. In the second cut, the P-BBF group had a significantly higher N offtake than the “CAN + TSP” reference.

Figure 15. N offtake of ryegrass as sum of 4 cuts ((1) 22 October 2021; (2) 5 May 2022; (3) 5 July 2022; (4) 26 October 2022). Each section of the bar represents the back-transformed median of the corresponding cut. Identical lower-case letters indicate no significant difference between the treatments for the corresponding cut (1–4) (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Identical upper-case letters indicate no significant difference between the main effects of the treatments. Pooled standard error of transformed data ~ 0.08 (1,2,3,4).

Fertilization with most of the BBFs significantly increased the total P offtake compared to the unfertilized reference (Figure 16). However, there were no overall significant differences in P offtake between P- and N-BBFs. In the first cut, the N-BBFs resulted in a significantly higher P offtake than the P-BBFs and the unfertilized reference. In contrast, in the second cut, the P-BBFs resulted in a significantly higher P offtake than the N-BBFs and the “CAN + TSP” reference. Both BBF groups showed significantly higher P offtake than the unfertilized reference. In the third cut, the N-BBFs led to a significantly higher P offtake than the P-BBFs and the “CAN + TSP” reference.

Figure 16. P offtake of ryegrass as the sum of four cuts ((1) 22 October 2021; (2) 5 May 2022; (3) 5 July 2022; (4) 26 October 2022). Each section of the bar represents the back-transformed median of the corresponding cut. Identical lower-case letters indicate no significant difference between the treatments for the corresponding cut (1–4) (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Identical upper-case letters indicate no significant difference between the main effects of the treatments. Pooled standard error of transformed data ~ 0.08 (1,2,3,4).

3.2.3. Heavy Metals in Ryegrass Biomass After Winter Wheat as a Main Crop

Heavy metal concentrations in ryegrass biomass showed significant differences only for molybdenum in the second cut. Here, the unfertilized control had a significantly higher Mo content than the treatments fertilized with the P-BBFs MO14 and CGO and the N-BBF OG2 (Table A6).

3.3. Soil-Related Characteristics After Winter Wheat and Ryegrass

After winter wheat in 2020/21 and another year of ryegrass, the fertilizer treatments did not result in significant differences in soil C_{org} or N_{min} concentrations. We, therefore, assume that long-term studies (>2 years) are needed to demonstrate effects on the soil C pool. The initial soil at the start of the trial had a pH of 6.5, which increased to 7.1 or 7.2 for all containers at the end of the trial. However, the differences in pH between the containers were very small (<0.1) and, thus, irrelevant for any differences in nutrient availability between the treatments.

The fertilizer treatments had a significant effect on soil P(CAL) concentration at the end of the trial (Figure 17). The N-BBF group led to a significantly higher soil P concentration than the P-BBF group. Both groups accumulated significantly more P, which is potentially plant-available, in the soil, than the references, which were not fertilized with P. While the N-BBFs showed no significant differences between the different fertilizer sources, the variation in CAL-P between the treatments fertilized with the P-BBFs was considerable. Containers fertilized with MO14 had significantly lower CAL-P levels than those fertilized with OPU, CGO, and ADC.

Figure 17. Mean P(CAL) concentration in soil samples taken after ryegrass in 2022 for all treatments. Blue bars represent P-BBFs, orange bars N-BBFs, and black bars the unfertilized (Control 0) and mineral references. The mean values of fertilizers with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Pooled standard error of transformed data 0.13.

3.4. Nutrient Offtake of Winter Wheat and Ryegrass in the Crop Cycle

The fertilization treatments differed highly significantly from each other in total N offtake of the winter wheat and ryegrass crop cycle. The BBFs had a significantly higher total N offtake compared to the unfertilized control and “only TSP”. Here “only CAN” and “CAN + TSP” were significantly higher than the N-BBF group. The P-BBF group also showed significantly higher N offtake than the N-BBF group (Figure 18). The P-BBFs CGO, OPU, MB1 and MO14 showed the highest total N offtake for all treatments. The N-BBF BA6 did not differ significantly from the unfertilized control.

Figure 18. Mean values of N offtake of winter wheat and ryegrass for all treatments. Blue bars represent P-BBFs, orange bars N-BBFs, black bars the unfertilized (Control 0) and mineral references. Treatments with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Pooled standard error 0.69.

The fertilization treatments differed highly significantly from each other in total P offtake of the winter wheat and ryegrass crop cycle. The BBFs had a significantly higher total P offtake compared to the unfertilized control and “only TSP”. The P-BBF group showed significantly higher P offtake than the N-BBF group (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Mean values of P offtake of winter wheat and ryegrass for all treatments. Blue bars represent P-BBFs, orange bars N-BBFs, black bars the unfertilized (Control 0) and mineral references. The treatments with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other (Tukey’s HSD, $\alpha = 0.05$). Pooled standard error ~ 87.9 .

4. Discussion

4.1. Winter Wheat in 2020/21

The higher fluctuation of SPAD values following N-BBF treatments (Figure 6) compared to P-BBF treatments (Figure 7) may be caused by the different source materials, organic N forms of the BBFs, and, therefore, their different N availability over the growing period of winter wheat. It has been shown that the release of N by recycled fertilizers depends on the C/N ratio of the original material and the processing [37,38]. In contrast, a cross-European field study with 16 N-BBFs (also BA6, PAL, MO13, and OG2) found no relationship between the C/N ratio or other BBF properties (pH, total N, NH_4^+ , NO_3^- , DM, and total C content) and the agronomic performance of the BBFs [39]. In our study, the differences in SPAD values between treatments correlated more with the ammonium content of the fertilizers than with the C/N ratio or any specific processing technology. This indicates that the short-term N fertilization value was influenced by the readily available N in the fertilizers. On the other hand, the medium/long-term N mineralization in this study may not have been synchronized with plant uptake. The N-BBF group resulted in significantly lower grain N concentrations than the mineral N reference group (CAN + TSP, only CAN), which implies a poorer N supply by the BBFs (Figure 9). In addition to the asynchrony between N release and crop N demand, recycled N fertilizers do not provide all of the N in the year of application [40,41], which may have resulted in lower N availability compared to the mineral references in this study.

The lower SPAD values in the N-BBF treatments (Figure 6), lower total N offtake (Figure 18), lower grain N concentrations (Figure 9), lack of effect on plant-available N_{min} in soil after winter wheat, and a generally low residual value in the subsequent crop ryegrass (Figures 14–16) all indicate that considerable amounts of N may have already been lost by volatilization and/or leaching after application. However, there were exceptions, including SIF and OG2 (Figure 15). Another reason for the lower total N offtake in the N-BBFs could

be the late application of the second fertilizer dose (Table 2). The sharp increase in the SPAD values in BBF treatments between the end of May and the beginning of June and the strong approximation of the SPAD values of N-BBF treatments compared to those of the mineral references indicate a high N supply by the N-BBFs in warm and humid conditions [42]. Thus, due to the asynchronous release of N to the plant demand, large amounts of N from the BBFs may have been mineralized too late to meet the crops' needs. In summary, the findings of this study suggest that N-BBFs were less effective than conventional fertilizers in this trial year with the split application.

In the field study by Müller et al. [39], the total N amount supplied by N-BBFs was applied in one dose in spring. Here, the N-BBFs PAL, BA6, OG2, and MO13 did not differ from each other with respect to yield or N offtake of crops. Based on the suggestions of Müller et al. [39] and the first-year fertilizing effect in this study, we conclude that it may be beneficial for practitioners to apply the full fertilizer amount at one dose early in the growing period and to incorporate the N-BBFs into the soil after fertilization to minimize environmental influences.

The clear differences between the P- and N-BBFs in total N, P offtake (Figures 18 and 19), straw yield, and grain N and P concentration (Figures 8–10) are possibly due to the different dynamics of P and N fertilizing effects. The P-BBFs not only supplied P, but some of them also provided considerable amounts of N, in particular OPU, MB1, and MBC (Table 1). As all P-BBF treatments received the full dosage of CAN, more N could be mineralized in total in these treatments during the growing season than in the other treatments. As a struvite, CGO in particular is known to release up to 100% N over time [37]. However, chicken manure and meat and bone meal can also contribute relevant amounts to N fertilization in the same year of application [41,43]. This could explain why CGO, MB1, and OPU showed higher grain N concentrations. However, in general, the differences between the BBFs are not very pronounced, which was expected due to the favorable weather conditions in 2021.

4.2. Residual Value of BBFs in Ryegrass 2021/22

The ryegrass sown after winter wheat to assess the residual fertilization effect of the BBFs showed significantly higher dry matter and N and P offtakes with the BBFs than with the unfertilized control in the sum of all four cuts (Figures 14–16). Differences in dry matter and nutrient offtake between treatments were most pronounced in the first cut in October, and, in particular, in the second cut at the beginning of May.

The N-BBFs PAL, BA6, and MAL did not contribute to N fertilization in the second cut, as they showed comparable dry mass and N offtake to the unfertilized control. With regard to P offtake in the second cut, BA6 was the only N-BBF that did not differ significantly from the unfertilized reference. This indicates that this N-BBF had a lower residual value than mineral fertilizers in this study, but that this lower N supply had little effect on P uptake.

The cross-European field study by Müller et al. [39] demonstrated that the residual value of N-BBFs was similar to that of the mineral N fertilizers at all trial sites. The container trial was designed to simulate field conditions by using large-volume pots (240 L each). However, a higher mineralization of the BBFs due to comparatively high soil temperatures in the containers cannot be ruled out. The N from the late second N dose in 2021 during warm and humid conditions may have been completely mineralized, taken up by the plants, or lost to the atmosphere between the harvest of the winter wheat and the establishment of the ryegrass roots. Furthermore, the references and P-BBF treatments fertilized with mineral N showed significantly higher values for total dry matter and N offtake. The P-BBFs did not differ significantly from the CAN reference, suggesting that the residual effect of mineral N fertilization was responsible for this effect. In general, the total N offtake of ryegrass correlated strongly with the N offtake of winter wheat, indicating that N-BBFs with more accessible N forms also contribute to a greater extent to short-term residual fertilizer effects, similar to CAN. However, this tendency may change in the long term. The lower efficiency of less available N sources may be overcompensated in subsequent years,

as has been shown for other recycled fertilizers, while mineral fertilizers do not contribute to the build-up of N pools in soil [41,44,45].

The P-BBF group resulted in significantly higher dry matter and N and P offtakes in the second cut than the N-BBFs and the unfertilized control. The higher P offtake in the P-BBF treatments may be the consequence of a nitrogen supply effect of BBFs that are not incinerated or pyrolyzed during production as ADC and MBC are, because a general positive P fertilization effect was not recognizable (no difference between the fully fertilized reference and the reference fertilized with CAN only). After the winter and due to rising soil temperatures in May, the organically bound P may have been mineralized, accompanied by a N release. Other studies have also shown that organic P fertilizers can have a significant effect on the yield and nutrient uptake of the succeeding crop and can provide additional N during their decomposition [46–49]. With regard to the struvite-based BBFs (CGO), struvite is considered as a slow-release fertilizer that does not dissolve immediately but can be mineralized by the plant over a longer period of time, potentially also contributing to the N nutrition of the succeeding crop [50].

MBC supplied considerable amounts of N, while the biomass yield of ryegrass was lower with MO14, which supplied less N (Table A3). Thus, the differences between P-BBFs cannot be explained solely by the additional N supply and are probably also related to the synchronization of N and P release, e.g., from magnesium ammonium phosphates in some BBFs and the nutrient demand of the crop. However, these release patterns were not determined in this study and would require further investigations dedicated to this aspect.

The effect of all fertilizer residuals on dry matter and nutrient uptake decreased over time (third and fourth cut), indicating that the residual value probably diminished in the summer after fertilization of the main crop. In general, the P-BBFs tended to have a higher residual fertilizing value than the N-BBFs. However, a general statement on BBFs cannot be made, since some N-BBFs, including SIF (animal and plant-based) and OG2 (horn meal), also had high residual effects on dry matter and N uptake. Statistically, the residual effect of all BBFs on dry matter and N and P offtake was not distinguishable from the references fertilized with the mineral fertilizers CAN and TSP, as was also found for N-BBFs by Müller et al. [39]. For N-BBFs, the lack of residual value can be seen as a desirable effect in agricultural practice as N is typically only applied to the main crop and it is not expedient for N to be lost to the environment after crop growth.

For P fertilizers on the other hand, a residual fertilizing value can be seen as a desirable effect as the less mobile P is less prone to environmental losses between growing seasons than N. P BBFs may release P more slowly than mineral P fertilizers such as TSP, where all the P is water-soluble. Therefore, P-BBFs could be less susceptible to precipitation into plant-unavailable P forms between growing seasons and deliver nutrients to subsequent crops more sustainably. Therefore, the residual effects of P-BBFs could fit in with farmers' common practice of applying P only once in a crop rotation.

4.3. Nutrient Offtake and Fertilizer Replacement Values of the Winter Wheat, Ryegrass Crop Cycle

The fact that the P-BBF group showed a significantly higher total N offtake than the N-BBFs and references in the crop rotation can be explained by the overall better growth, probably caused by the additional N the P-BBFs brought into the system (Table 3). However, it cannot be stated that the P-BBFs with the highest additional N content also have proportionally higher N offtakes in the crop rotation. For example, the P-BBFs with the highest N offtake (OPU and CGO) added different amounts of N to the system (138 kg ha⁻¹, 38 kg ha⁻¹) but showed no differences in the results. The P-BBFs with the lowest N offtake (ADC, 1 kg N ha⁻¹; MBC, 79 kg N ha⁻¹) also showed no relationship between the amount of N fertilized through the P-BBFs and the N offtake in the crop cycle.

In terms of total P offtake, the P-BBFs resulted in comparable or even slightly higher yields than the fully fertilized reference. Since there is no P-fertilization effect in this crop rotation (only CAN shows a higher yield than CAN + TSP), this effect cannot be attributed to the improved P nutrition by P-BBFs, but rather to the additional N release by P-BBFs in

ryegrass, which may have stabilized yields. The lower P offtake of the N-BBFs resulted from the lower overall biomass production compared to the P-BBFs and the conventionally fertilized references.

We conclude that the additional N fertilized by the P-BBFs may be relevant for the fertilizer effectiveness in the whole crop rotation. However, the amount of N applied by P-BBFs does not correlate with the N offtake in the crop rotation. We assume that, depending on the N or N/P (struvite) compounds in P-BBFs, the N mobilization pattern is synchronized with plant demand or the additional N is either lost or remains unavailable to plants. BBFs that were efficient in the main crop were equally efficient in the second crop. This can be seen in the fertilizer replacement values (Tables A3 and A4) and a high positive correlation between winter wheat and ryegrass in total P and N offtake (0.55 and 0.74 (Pearson)). Although there was no significant effect of P fertilization in the first and second crop, the fertilizer replacement value of the P-BBFs in the crop rotation ranged between 105% and 161%, with an average PFRV of 145%. The fertilizer replacement value of the 6 N-BBFs in this trial ranged between 47 and 80% and averaged 62% in winter wheat (Table A3), which is comparable to results by Müller et al. [35].

4.4. Further Observations

Differences in heavy metal concentrations in winter wheat grain and ryegrass biomass following BBF application compared to the mineral references are negligible due to their generally low levels. Therefore, the BBFs investigated in this study did not pose a higher risk of heavy metal concentrations in crops than the conventional mineral fertilizers CAN and TSP.

The BBFs and reference treatments tested did not result in any significant changes in soil C_{org} or N_{min} . However, the soil pH increased from 6.5 to approx. 7.1 for all treatments (including “control”) over the two years. Nitrate nutrition and buffering effects of C_{org} contents in BBFs can be excluded, as applied quantities were too small and the same effects were observed for the unfertilized controls. We, therefore, assume that this is an effect of soil stabilization more than two years after mixing.

The P-BBFs and references with TSP resulted in lower soil concentrations of plant-available P compared to the N-BBFs (Figure 17). The reason for this may be a lower P offtake in N-BBF treatments due to the generally stronger growth of crops treated with P-BBFs and mineral references. This assumption is probably supported by the similarly low soil P concentration in containers treated with the N-BBF SIF, which also resulted in comparably high values to the P-BBFs for ryegrass dry matter as well as N and P offtake.

4.5. Remarks on the Experimental Approach Chosen

The use of 240 L containers for a crop growth and fertilization experiment proved to be very suitable for a two-year experiment and at the same time a relatively low-cost solution to mimic field conditions. The container volume was found to be large enough to allow the full crop development, and the plants behaved similarly (stress response, tillering, flowering, senescence) to those in field conditions on neighboring fields over the two years. This was certainly the most important benefit. Exposing crops to outside conditions while protecting them from the major external risks of animals and droughts worked well. However, it was limited in this study by prolonged rainy conditions that caused the grain loss in winter wheat. It can be assumed that the information obtained through container studies is of greater value compared to classical pot trials in terms of the transfer of results and recommendations to field conditions. This statement is underlined by similar fertilizer replacement values for N-BBFs in the field study by Müller et al. [39].

Due to the feasibility of multi-year trials, the crop rotation of winter wheat and ryegrass has been extended to include maize in 2023 and ryegrass in 2023/24. Longer use is also planned. Furthermore, it is possible to measure the leaching of nutrients or environmental toxins by taking frequent samples at the valve at the bottom of the containers. In summary, this approach can be recommended without restriction for comparable research questions.

5. Conclusions

The NFRV based on N offtake and control ranged from 47% to 80% in winter wheat. Not all N-BBFs resulted in a similarly high N concentration in wheat straw as the mineral references. However, incorporating N-BBFs to buffer environmental influences could help to make the fertilizing effect of lower-performing BBFs more reliable.

P-BBFs applied in a crop rotation (two years, winter wheat followed by ryegrass) orientated towards agricultural practice, where P is commonly applied for crop cycles, showed at least similar P supply effectiveness as the conventional mineral TSP fertilizer in a P-deficient soil. The PFRV based on P offtake and control ranged between 105% and 161% for the winter wheat–ryegrass crop cycle. The P-BBFs not subjected to incineration or pyrolysis during their production, where N is lost, showed that the N contained in these products can have a measurable positive effect on the following crop. In this study, the N from P-BBFs appeared to be released only through the mineralization in spring 2021. However, this residual N effect disappeared after the spring in the following crop and was no longer detectable in summer. We, therefore, assume that the N contained in P-BBFs can be considered positive and unproblematic for losses during winter and could, thus, act as a starter fertilizer already in the soil for the following crop in spring.

In general, the application of BBFs did not result in any significant changes in C_{org} , N_{min} or heavy metals in the soil. The P-BBFs appeared to have higher residual values than N-BBFs, but these residual values were comparable to those of mineral fertilizers. While P-BBFs proved to be a sustainable and reliable nutrient source for a crop cycle, the N-BBFs applied as the main crop fertilizer were found to be more susceptible to environmental influences and could, therefore, be less easy to apply for professional practitioners for effective plant nutrition.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Appendix A

Table A1. Adjusted marginal means of every second SPAD measurement in N-BBF treatments in 2021 using Fisher’s LSD test. Within a crop and trait, mean values of fertilizer with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other ($p < 0.005$).

Date	April 6	April 21	May 4	May 19	May 27	June 10	June 16
Reference 1 (N + P)	42.7 a	46.3 b	49.0 d	45.9 b	46.7 a	54.6 c	55.3 b
BA6	41.0 a	42.8 a	45.0 cd	42.3 a	44.9 a	49.4 a	49.9 a
MAL	42.1 a	45.2 ab	46.1 bc	45.3 b	46.2 a	53.2 bc	53.0 ab
MO13	41.1 a	43.6 a	44.2 ab	44.8 b	46.7 a	51.7 ab	52.8 ab

Table A1. *Cont.*

Date	April 6	April 21	May 4	May 19	May 27	June 10	June 16
OG2	41.4 a	42.7 a	43.4 a	43.5 ab	45.4 a	49.8 a	50.4 a
PAL	42.3 a	44.6 ab	47.3 cd	44.1 ab	46.2 a	50.4 a	52.6 ab
SIF	42.7 a	44.1 ab	45.6 bc	44.6 ab	46.7 a	51.5 ab	53.3 ab

Table A2. Estimated marginal means of every second SPAD measurement in P-BBF treatments in 2021 using Fisher's LSD test. Within a crop and trait, mean values of fertilizer with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other ($p < 0.005$).

Date	April 6	April 21	May 4	May 19	May 27	June 10	June 16
Reference 1 (N + P)	43.1 bc	46.2 bc	46.8 a	45.9 ab	46.3 ab	54.6 bc	55.3 a
ADC	40.6 ab	44.3 ab	45.8 a	45.2 ab	45.9 a	52.3 ab	54.9 a
MBC	39.5 a	41.8 a	45.2 a	44.1 a	46.3 ab	51.8 a	55.1 a
MB1	42.4 abc	46.6 bc	46.5 a	45.6 ab	48.4 bc	55.4 c	56.9 a
MO14	44.3 c	44.2 ab	47.1 a	46.7 b	48.4 c	56.1 c	56.2 a
OPU	42.9 bc	44.6 b	44.9 a	45.7 ab	46.8 abc	56.2 c	55.8 a
CGO	43.6 bc	48.7 c	46.6 a	46.9 b	48.2 bc	56.3 c	55.7 a

Table A3. Agronomic efficiency and nitrogen fertilizer replacement values with standard errors of N-BBFs based on winter wheat.

N Treatment	N-AE (g N Offtake (g N Fertilized) ⁻¹)	NFRV (%)	N-AE (g N Offtake (g N Fertilized) ⁻¹)	NFRV (%)
	Based on Reference 3 (Only TSP)		Based on Control	
PAL	1.04 ± 0.06	78 ± 0.06	0.99 ± 0.06	77 ± 0.06
BA6	0.67 ± 0.06	49 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.06	47 ± 0.05
SIF	0.96 ± 0.06	71 ± 0.06	0.90 ± 0.06	70 ± 0.06
MAL	1.09 ± 0.06	81 ± 0.06	1.03 ± 0.06	80 ± 0.06
OG2	0.71 ± 0.06	53 ± 0.05	0.65 ± 0.06	51 ± 0.06
MO13	0.67 ± 0.06	50 ± 0.05	0.61 ± 0.06	47 ± 0.05
CAN + TSP	1.35 ± 0.06	-	1.29 ± 0.06	-

PAL = Palaterra CV, BA6 = Bioagenasol, SIF = SIFORGA-BIO, MAL = Maltaflor bio, OG2 = Øgro N15, MO13 = Monterra, CAN = calcium ammonium nitrate, TSP = triple superphosphate, AE = agronomic efficiency, NFRV = nitrogen fertilizer replacement value.

Table A4. Agronomic efficiency and nitrogen fertilizer replacement values with standard errors of N BBFs based on the crop rotation of winter wheat and ryegrass.

N Treatment	N-AE (g N Offtake (g N Fertilized) ⁻¹)	NFRV (%)	N-AE (g N Offtake (g N Fertilized) ⁻¹)	NFRV (%)
	Based on Reference 3 (Only TSP)		Based on Control	
PAL	0.61 ± 0.15	77 ± 23	0.55 ± 0.15	75 ± 25
BA6	0.41 ± 0.15	52 ± 21	0.35 ± 0.15	48 ± 22
SIF	0.61 ± 0.15	76 ± 23	0.55 ± 0.15	74 ± 25
MAL	0.65 ± 0.15	82 ± 24	0.59 ± 0.15	80 ± 26
OG2	0.50 ± 0.15	63 ± 22	0.44 ± 0.15	60 ± 23
MO13	0.50 ± 0.15	57 ± 22	0.39 ± 0.15	53 ± 23
CAN + TSP	0.45 ± 0.15	-	0.66 ± 0.15	-

PAL = Palaterra CV, BA6 = Bioagenasol, SIF = SIFORGA-BIO, MAL = Maltaflor bio, OG2 = Øgro N15, MO13 = Monterra, CAN = calcium ammonium nitrate, TSP = triple superphosphate, AE = agronomic efficiency, NFRV = nitrogen fertilizer replacement value.

Table A5. Agronomic efficiency and phosphorus replacement values with standard errors of P-BBFs in the crop rotation of winter wheat and ryegrass based on Reference 2 (left) and unfertilized control (right).

P Treatment	P-AE	PFRV	P-AE	PFRV
	(mg P Offtake (g P Fertilized) ⁻¹)	(%)	(mg P Offtake (g P Fertilized) ⁻¹)	(%)
	Based on Reference 2 (Only CAN)		Based on Control	
MO14	77.8 ± 51.4	−951 ± 4776	235.0 ± 51.0	158 ± 64
MB1	75.7 ± 54.6	−924 ± 4648	232.8 ± 54.2	156 ± 65
OPU	82.2 ± 51.5	−1004 ± 5039	239.4 ± 51.1	161 ± 65
CGO	80.7 ± 51.5	−985 ± 4947	237.9 ± 51.0	160 ± 65
ADC	−0.32 ± 52.3	4 ± 638	156.9 ± 51.8	105 ± 50
MBC	39.74 ± 51.5	−485 ± 2497	196.9 ± 51.1	132 ± 57
CAN + TSP	−8.19 ± 40.8	-	149.0 ± 51.1	-

MO14 = Monterra, MB1 = meat and bone meal, OPU = chicken manure, CGO = struvite, ADC = AshDec, MBC = manure biochar, CAN = calcium ammonium nitrate, TSP = triple superphosphate, AE = agronomic efficiency, PFRV = phosphorus fertilizer replacement value.

Table A6. Heavy metal concentration in the second cut of ryegrass for all treatments, in mg g⁻¹ for iron (Fe), manganese (Mn) and zinc (Zn), and in µg g⁻¹ for molybdenum (Mo), lead (Pb), nickel (Ni) and copper (Cu). The mean values of heavy metals for treatments with at least one identical letter are not significantly different from each other (Tukey's HSD, α = 0.05). For heavy metal values without letters, no significant differences between treatments were detected by Tukey's test.

Treatment	Element							
	Fe	Mn	Zn	Mo	Pb	Ni	Cu	
	mg g ⁻¹			µg g ⁻¹				
References	Control	0.14	0.017	0.15	1.32 _b	0.82	1.88	3.74
	CAN + TSP	0.18	0.018	0.15	1.02 _{ab}	0.98	1.90	2.38
	Only CAN	0.18	0.017	0.19	1.02 _{ab}	1.04	1.81	2.78
	Only TSP	0.15	0.016	0.13	1.14 _{ab}	0.84	1.90	3.23
P-BBFs	MB1	0.16	0.017	0.16	0.95 _{ab}	0.91	1.73	2.89
	CGO	0.17	0.017	0.14	0.91 _a	0.74	1.84	2.17
	ADC	0.15	0.017	0.12	1.09 _{ab}	0.65	1.80	2.04
	OPU	0.19	0.019	0.21	1.10 _{ab}	0.99	1.67	3.28
	MO14	0.19	0.018	0.18	0.94 _a	0.98	1.85	3.32
	MBC	0.16	0.017	0.15	1.09 _{ab}	0.79	1.78	2.03
N-BBFs	OG2	0.15	0.016	0.19	0.93 _a	0.92	1.77	4.18
	MO13	0.15	0.016	0.11	1.12 _{ab}	0.72	1.93	2.21
	PAL	0.16	0.017	0.15	1.16 _{ab}	0.87	1.78	3.39
	BA6	0.13	0.017	0.16	1.16 _{ab}	0.73	1.95	4.01
	SIF	0.17	0.017	0.16	1.01 _{ab}	0.86	1.74	2.60
	MAL	0.14	0.018	0.13	1.16 _{ab}	0.67	1.85	2.39

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